

Web of Science™ Search Queries

Most common synonyms and variations related to primary keywords were included to provide more comprehensive coverage of the topic. Whenever possible, review articles were excluded by applying "Quick Filters" to the "Document Types" category.

Nano and Microplastic focus selection

Search Query History

(TS=(nanoplas*)) OR TS=(microplas*)

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((((TS=(nanoplas*)) OR TS=(microplas*)) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)) AND TS=(Food) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((((TS=(nanoplas*)) OR TS=(microplas*)) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)) AND TS=(Health) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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(((TS=(nanoplas*) OR TS=(microplas*)) AND TS=(Environment)) AND (TS=("Food wrapping") OR TS=("Food container") OR TS=("Food packaging materials") OR TS=("Food packag*") OR TS=("Food encasement"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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Bioplastics

Search Query History

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plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")) AND TS=(Environment)) AND ((TS=("Soil health") OR TS=("Soil quality") OR TS=("Soil fertil*") OR TS=("Soil condition*") OR TS=("Soil functional*") OR TS=("Soil product*") OR TS=("Land quality") OR TS=("Soil ecosystem*")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")))) AND TS=(Health)) AND ((TS=("Water Quality") OR TS=("Water Purity") OR TS=("Water Composition") OR TS=("Hydrolog* Quality") OR TS=("Water Condition*") OR TS=("Water Standard*") OR TS=("Water Characteristic*") OR TS=("Chemical Quality of Water") OR TS=("Physical Quality of Water") OR TS=("Water Contamination Level*") OR TS=("Water Pollution Assessment") OR TS=("Water Suitability")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31))

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DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)))

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Types)

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TS=(Environment)) AND ((TS=(Metabolom*) OR TS=("Metabolome analysis") OR TS=(Metab*) OR TS=(Fluxomics))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)))

(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")))) AND TS=(Environment)) AND ((TS=(Metabolom*) OR TS=("Metabolome analysis") OR TS=(Metab*) OR TS=(Fluxomics))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31))) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")))) AND TS=(Food)) AND ((TS=(Metabolom*) OR TS=("Metabolome analysis") OR TS=(Metab*) OR TS=(Fluxomics))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31))) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")))) AND TS=(Environment)) AND ((TS=("Risk assessment") OR TS=("Risk analysis") OR TS=("Risk management") OR TS=("Hazard assessment") OR TS=("Threat assessment") OR TS=("Vulnerability assessment") OR TS=("Safety assessment") OR TS=("Impact assessment") OR TS=("Exposure assessment") OR TS=("Risk characterization")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)))

(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based

plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")) AND TS=(Health)) AND ((TS=("Risk assessment") OR TS=("Risk analysis") OR TS=("Risk management") OR TS=("Hazard assessment") OR TS=("Threat assessment") OR TS=("Vulnerability assessment") OR TS=("Safety assessment") OR TS=("Impact assessment") OR TS=("Exposure assessment") OR TS=("Risk characterization")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)))

(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")) AND TS=(Food)) AND ((TS=("Risk assessment") OR TS=("Risk analysis") OR TS=("Risk management") OR TS=("Hazard assessment") OR TS=("Threat assessment") OR TS=("Vulnerability assessment") OR TS=("Safety assessment") OR TS=("Impact assessment") OR TS=("Exposure assessment") OR TS=("Risk characterization")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)))

(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")) AND TS=(Food)) AND ((TS=("Risk assessment") OR TS=("Risk analysis") OR TS=("Risk management") OR TS=("Hazard assessment") OR TS=("Threat assessment") OR TS=("Vulnerability assessment") OR TS=("Safety assessment") OR TS=("Impact assessment") OR TS=("Exposure assessment") OR TS=("Risk characterization")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31))) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")) AND TS=(Environment)) AND ((TS=("Risk assessment") OR TS=("Risk analysis") OR TS=("Risk management") OR TS=("Hazard assessment") OR TS=("Threat assessment") OR TS=("Vulnerability assessment") OR TS=("Safety assessment") OR TS=("Impact assessment") OR TS=("Exposure assessment") OR TS=("Risk characterization")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31))) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")))) AND TS=(Environment)) AND (((TS=("Food contaminat*")) OR TS=("Food Pollutant")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)))

(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")))) AND TS=(Health)) AND (((TS=("Food contaminat*")) OR TS=("Food Pollutant")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)))

(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")))) AND TS=(Food)) AND (((TS=("Food contaminat*")) OR TS=("Food Pollutant")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)))

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OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")) AND TS=(Environment)) AND (((TS=("Food chain")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31))

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(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")))) AND TS=(Health)) AND (((TS=("Food chain")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)))) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

TS=(Health)) AND (((TS=("Food chain")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)))) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")))) AND TS=(Environment)) AND (((TS=("Food wrapping") OR TS=("Food container") OR TS=("Food packaging materials") OR TS=("Food packag*") OR TS=("Food encasement")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31))))

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OR TS=("Food packag*") OR TS=("Food encasement")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31))) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

(((((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*")))) AND TS=(Environment)) AND (((TS=("Food wrapping") OR TS=("Food container") OR TS=("Food packaging materials") OR TS=("Food packag*") OR TS=("Food encasement")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31))) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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Metals/Metal Oxides

Search Query History

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interaction*")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude –
Document Types)

((((TS=("Metal* Microparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Microparticl*")) OR (TS=("Metal* Nanoparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Nanoparticl*")) AND TS=(Food)) AND
(TS=("Mechanistic") OR TS=("Mechanism* of action") OR TS=("Mechanistic pathway*")
OR TS=("Molecular interaction*") OR TS=("Biological interaction*") OR TS=("Causal
relationship*") OR TS=("Functional interaction*") OR TS=("Physiological mechanism*") OR
TS=("Interventional mechanism*") OR TS=("Dynamic interaction*") OR TS=("Systemic
interaction*")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude –
Document Types)

((((TS=("Metal* Microparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Microparticl*")) OR (TS=("Metal* Nanoparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Nanoparticl*")) AND TS=(Environment)) AND ((TS=(Metabolom*) OR TS=("Metabolome analysis") OR TS=(Metab*) OR TS=(Fluxomics))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((((TS=("Metal* Microparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Microparticl*")) OR (TS=("Metal* Nanoparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Nanoparticl*")) AND TS=(Health)) AND ((TS=(Metabolom*) OR TS=("Metabolome analysis") OR TS=(Metab*) OR TS=(Fluxomics))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((((TS=("Metal* Microparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Microparticl*")) OR (TS=("Metal* Nanoparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Nanoparticl*")) AND TS=(Food)) AND ((TS=(Metabolom*) OR TS=("Metabolome analysis") OR TS=(Metab*) OR TS=(Fluxomics))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((((TS=("Metal* Microparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Microparticl*")) OR (TS=("Metal* Nanoparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Nanoparticl*")) AND TS=(Environment)) AND ((TS=("Risk assessment") OR TS=("Risk analysis") OR TS=("Risk management") OR TS=("Hazard assessment") OR TS=("Threat assessment") OR TS=("Vulnerability assessment") OR TS=("Safety assessment") OR TS=("Impact assessment") OR TS=("Exposure assessment") OR TS=("Risk characterization")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((((TS=("Metal* Microparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Microparticl*")) OR (TS=("Metal* Nanoparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Nanoparticl*")) AND TS=(Health)) AND ((TS=("Risk assessment") OR TS=("Risk analysis") OR TS=("Risk management") OR TS=("Hazard assessment") OR TS=("Threat assessment") OR TS=("Vulnerability assessment") OR TS=("Safety assessment") OR TS=("Impact assessment") OR TS=("Exposure assessment") OR TS=("Risk characterization")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((((TS=("Metal* Microparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Microparticl*")) OR (TS=("Metal* Nanoparticl*")) OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Nanoparticl*")) AND TS=(Food)) AND ((TS=("Risk assessment") OR TS=("Risk analysis") OR TS=("Risk management") OR TS=("Hazard assessment") OR TS=("Threat assessment") OR TS=("Vulnerability assessment") OR TS=("Safety assessment") OR TS=("Impact assessment") OR TS=("Exposure assessment") OR TS=("Risk characterization")))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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((TS=("Metal* Microparticl*") OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Microparticl*") OR TS=("Metal* Nanoparticl*") OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Nanoparticl*")) AND TS=(Health) AND (TS=("Food contaminat*") OR TS=("Food Pollutant*"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)

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((TS=("Metal* Microparticl*") OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Microparticl*") OR TS=("Metal* Nanoparticl*") OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Nanoparticl*")) AND TS=(Health) AND (TS=("Structural Investigation") OR TS=("Physical charact*") OR TS=("Morphological Characterizat*") OR TS=("Structural Features Analysis") OR TS=("Crystallographic Analysis") OR TS=("Structural Assessment") OR TS=("Structural Profiling") OR TS=("Microstructural Characterization") OR TS=("Material Characterization"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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OR TS=(Decomposition) OR TS=(Biodegradat*) OR TS=(Photodegradation) OR
TS=(Thermaldegradation) OR TS=(Chemicaldegradation))) AND
DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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TS=(Photodegradation) OR TS=(Thermaldegradation) OR TS=(Chemicaldegradation)))
AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

Plastic Additives

Search Query History

TS=(*Plastic additiv*) OR TS=(*plastic modifier*) OR TS=(Plasticizer*) OR TS=(*plastic stabilizers*) OR TS=(*plastic blending agent*)

(TS=(*Plastic additiv*) OR TS=(*plastic modifier*) OR TS=(Plasticizer*) OR TS=(*plastic stabilizers*) OR TS=(*plastic blending agent*)) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)

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((TS=(*Plastic additiv*) OR TS=(*plastic modifier*) OR TS=(Plasticizer*) OR TS=(*plastic stabilizers*) OR TS=(*plastic blending agent*)) AND TS=(Health) AND (TS=(Agricult*) OR TS=(Agronomy*) OR TS=(Farm*) OR TS=(Horticult*) OR TS=(Crop Product*) OR TS=(Cultivat*) OR TS=(Agroeco*) OR TS=(Land Use*) OR TS=(Crop Science*) OR TS=(Farming System*))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS=("Plasticizer*") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Food) AND (TS=("Agricult*") OR TS=("Agronomy") OR TS=("Farm*") OR TS=("Horticult*") OR TS=("Crop Product*") OR TS=("Cultivat*") OR TS=("Agroeco*") OR TS=("Land Use") OR TS=("Crop Science") OR TS=("Farming System*"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS=("Plasticizer*") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Health) AND (TS=("Soil health") OR TS=("Soil quality") OR TS=("Soil fertil*") OR TS=("Soil condition*") OR TS=("Soil functional*") OR TS=("Soil product*") OR TS=("Land quality") OR TS=("Soil ecosystem*"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS=("Plasticizer*") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Food) AND (TS=("Soil health") OR TS=("Soil quality") OR TS=("Soil fertil*") OR TS=("Soil condition*") OR TS=("Soil functional*") OR TS=("Soil product*") OR TS=("Land quality") OR TS=("Soil ecosystem*"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS=("Plasticizer*") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Environment) AND (TS=("Water Quality") OR TS=("Water Purity") OR TS=("Water Composition") OR TS=("Hydrolog* Quality") OR TS=("Water Condition*") OR TS=("Water Standard*") OR TS=("Water Characteristic*") OR TS=("Chemical Quality of Water") OR TS=("Physical Quality of Water") OR TS=("Water Contamination Level*") OR TS=("Water Pollution Assessment") OR TS=("Water Suitability*"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS=("Plasticizer*") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Health) AND (TS=("Water Quality") OR TS=("Water Purity") OR TS=("Water Composition") OR TS=("Hydrolog* Quality") OR TS=("Water Condition*") OR TS=("Water Standard*") OR TS=("Water Characteristic*") OR TS=("Chemical Quality of Water") OR TS=("Physical Quality of Water") OR TS=("Water Contamination Level*") OR TS=("Water Pollution Assessment") OR TS=("Water Suitability*"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS=("Plasticizer*") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Food) AND

((TS=("Water Quality") OR TS=("Water Purity") OR TS=("Water Composition") OR TS=("Hydrolog* Quality") OR TS=("Water Condition*") OR TS=("Water Standard*") OR TS=("Water Characteristic*") OR TS=("Chemical Quality of Water") OR TS=("Physical Quality of Water") OR TS=("Water Contamination Level*") OR TS=("Water Pollution Assessment") OR TS=("Water Suitability"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS=("Plasticizer*") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Environment) AND (TS=("Air quality") OR TS=("Air Pollution Levels") OR TS=("Air Composition") OR TS=("Air Pollution Index") OR TS=("Air Quality Index") OR TS=("Ambient Air Quality") OR TS=("Air Purity") OR TS=("Air Clean*") OR TS=("Air Health") OR TS=("Airborne Contamin*") OR TS=("Air Quality Assessment") OR TS=("Outdoor Air Quality") OR TS=("Urban Air Quality") OR TS=("Land Air Quality"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)

((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS=("Plasticizer*") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Health) AND (TS=("Air quality") OR TS=("Air Pollution Levels") OR TS=("Air Composition") OR TS=("Air Pollution Index") OR TS=("Air Quality Index") OR TS=("Ambient Air Quality") OR TS=("Air Purity") OR TS=("Air Clean*") OR TS=("Air Health") OR TS=("Airborne Contamin*") OR TS=("Air Quality Assessment") OR TS=("Outdoor Air Quality") OR TS=("Urban Air Quality") OR TS=("Land Air Quality"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)

((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS=("Plasticizer*") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Food) AND (TS=("Air quality") OR TS=("Air Pollution Levels") OR TS=("Air Composition") OR TS=("Air Pollution Index") OR TS=("Air Quality Index") OR TS=("Ambient Air Quality") OR TS=("Air Purity") OR TS=("Air Clean*") OR TS=("Air Health") OR TS=("Airborne Contamin*") OR TS=("Air Quality Assessment") OR TS=("Outdoor Air Quality") OR TS=("Urban Air Quality") OR TS=("Land Air Quality"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)

((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS=("Plasticizer*") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Environment) AND (TS=("Toxicolog*") OR TS=("Toxic") OR TS=("Clinical effects") OR TS=("Toxicant") OR TS=("Adverse effect") OR TS=("Developmental toxicity"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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studies") OR TS=("Infection control*") OR TS=("Population health") OR TS=("Health
statistics"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)

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(TS=("Disease surveillance") OR TS=("Public health") OR TS=("Epidemiolog* studies") OR
TS=("Infection control*") OR TS=("Population health") OR TS=("Health statistics"))) AND
DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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TS=("Causal relationship*") OR TS=("Functional interaction*") OR TS=("Physiological
mechanism*") OR TS=("Interventional mechanism*") OR TS=("Dynamic interaction*") OR
TS=("Systemic interaction*"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article
(Exclude - Document Types)

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TS=("Molecular interaction*") OR TS=("Biological interaction*") OR TS=("Causal
relationship*") OR TS=("Functional interaction*") OR TS=("Physiological mechanism*") OR
TS=("Interventional mechanism*") OR TS=("Dynamic interaction*") OR TS=("Systemic
interaction*"))) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document
Types)

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((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS="(Plasticizer)") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Health) AND (TS="(Risk assessment") OR TS="(Risk analysis") OR TS="(Risk management") OR TS="(Hazard assessment") OR TS="(Threat assessment") OR TS="(Vulnerability assessment") OR TS="(Safety assessment") OR TS="(Impact assessment") OR TS="(Exposure assessment") OR TS="(Risk characterization")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS="(Plasticizer)") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Food) AND (TS="(Risk assessment") OR TS="(Risk analysis") OR TS="(Risk management") OR TS="(Hazard assessment") OR TS="(Threat assessment") OR TS="(Vulnerability assessment") OR TS="(Safety assessment") OR TS="(Impact assessment") OR TS="(Exposure assessment") OR TS="(Risk characterization")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS="(Plasticizer)") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Environment) AND (TS="(Food contaminat*") OR TS="(Food Pollutant")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)

((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS="(Plasticizer)") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Health) AND (TS="(Food contaminat*") OR TS="(Food Pollutant*")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)

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((TS=("*Plastic additiv*") OR TS=("*plastic modifier*") OR TS="(Plasticizer)") OR TS=("*plastic stabilizers*") OR TS=("*plastic blending agent*")) AND TS=(Health) AND (TS="(Food wrapping*") OR TS="(Food container*") OR TS="(Food packaging materials*") OR TS="(Food packag*") OR TS="(Food encasement*")) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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TS=("Microstructural Characterization") OR TS=("Material Characterization")) AND
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Characterizat") OR TS=("Structural Features Analysis") OR TS=("Crystallographic
Analysis") OR TS=("Structural Assessment") OR TS=("Structural Profiling") OR
TS=("Microstructural Characterization") OR TS=("Material Characterization"))) AND
DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((TS=("Plastic additiv") OR TS=("plastic modifier") OR TS=("Plasticizer") OR
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Analysis") OR TS=("Structural Assessment") OR TS=("Structural Profiling") OR
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DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

((TS=("Plastic additiv") OR TS=("plastic modifier") OR TS=("Plasticizer") OR
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AND (TS=("Chemical Analysis") OR TS=("Chemical charact") OR TS=("Chemical
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TS=("Chemical Characterization Studies") OR TS=("Chemical Composition Analysis") OR
TS=("Composition Characterization") OR TS=("Substance Characterization"))) AND
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Characterization Studies") OR TS=("Chemical Composition Analysis") OR TS=("Composition
Characterization") OR TS=("Substance Characterization"))) AND
DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)

((TS=("Plastic additiv") OR TS=("plastic modifier") OR TS=("Plasticizer") OR
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AND (TS=(degradat*) OR TS=(Decomposition) OR TS=(Biodegradat*) OR

TS=(Photodegradation) OR TS=(Thermaldegradation) OR TS=(Chemicaldegradation))) AND
DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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TS=(Thermaldegradation) OR TS=(Chemicaldegradation))) AND
DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

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TS=(Thermaldegradation) OR TS=(Chemicaldegradation))) AND
DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31) and Review Article (Exclude - Document Types)

Statistical Analysis of the Web of Science™ Database

Search Query History

((TS=(nanoplas*) OR TS=(microplas*)) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)) AND TS=(Environment)

((TS=(Bioplast*) OR TS=("Bio-based plast*") OR TS=("Bio*Plast*") OR TS=("Compostable* plast*") OR TS=("Bio-sourced plastic*") OR TS=("Sustainable plastic*") OR TS=("Biodegradable plastic*") OR TS=("Natural plastic*") OR TS=("Plant-based plastic*") OR TS=("Green plastic*") OR TS=("Renewable plastic*") OR TS=("Eco-friendly plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-derived plastic*") OR TS=("Environmental plastic*") OR TS=("Plastic* alternative*") OR TS=("Non-petroleum plastic*") OR TS=("Organic plastic*") OR TS=("Recyclable bioplastic*") OR TS=("Agricultural-based plastic*") OR TS=("Algae-based plastic*") OR TS=("Starch-based plastic*") OR TS=("Cellulose-based plastic*") OR TS=("Bio-polymer plastic*"))) AND TS=(Environment)) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)

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((TS=("Metal* Microparticl*") OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Microparticl*") OR (TS=("Metal* Nanoparticl*") OR TS=("Metal* Oxid* Nanoparticl*"))) AND TS=(Environment)) AND DOP=(2020-01-01/2024-12-31)